

N-(2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene)anthranilic acid as a Gravimetric Reagent for Copper(II)

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N-(2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene) anthranilic acid has been employed as a reagent for the gravimetric determination of copper(II). The solid Cu(II) complex formed possesses 1 : 1 metal-ligand stoichiometry and is found to exist as an unsolvated dimer. The Cu(II) complex displays a magnetic moment of 1.89 BM at 303 K. A non-planar dimeric structure is proposed to explain the observed fact.

METAL chelates of the Schiff bases have been recently reviewed by Holm¹. A large number of metal chelates of the Schiff bases are solid and have therefore found application in the gravimetric estimation of such metal ions. No systematic studies seem to have been carried out so far using N-(2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene) anthranilic acid (H₂NA). It is a diprotic tridentate ligand containing a carboxylic group, a phenolic hydroxyl group and a donor nitrogen atom. It forms solid metal chelates with Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Pd(II), Cd(II) and UO₂(II)². The copper chelate is insoluble in water and can thus form the basis of a quantitative separation procedure.

Experimental

Apparatus: The molecular weight determination was carried out using semi-micro Gallenkamp Ebuliometer. The electronic absorption spectra measurements were carried out using Uvispeck Hilger Spectrophotometer. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on Guoy apparatus.

Reagent: To an ethanolic solution of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (3.4 g.), anthranilic acid (2.7 g.) was added. The mixture was refluxed on a water bath in presence of piperidine as the condensing agent (2-3 drops) for 1 hr, when a transparent orange solution was obtained. After refluxing, the solution was allowed to stand overnight in a refrigerator for crystallisation. Orange crystals were formed which were separated, crystallised from ethanol and preserved in a vacuum desiccator. The yield was found quantitative, found C, 74.11; H, 4.39; N, 4.78; calc. for C₁₈H₁₃NO₃, C, 74.22; H, 4.46; N, 4.81%.

Procedure

Gravimetric determination of Copper(II):

A 10% solution of the reagent was prepared in aqueous ethanol. 24.9690 g. of AnalaR copper sulphate was dissolved in a litre of distilled water to

give Cu(II) solution which was then standardized iodometrically.

An aliquot of the Cu(II) solution was taken in a 250 ml pyrex beaker and its pH was adjusted between 3.7 to 4.7 with acetic acid-sodium acetate buffer. To this solution the reagent was added gradually with constant stirring till no further formation of the yellowish green precipitate took place. The contents of the flask were heated to 95°-100° for 20 min., cooled and filtered through a weighed sintered glass crucible. The precipitate was washed with warm aqueous ethanol till it was free from the reagent as well as the sulphate ions. It was dried at 100°. Analyses gave Cu, 17.97%; N, 3.86%; Calcd. for Cu₂(C₁₈H₁₁NO₃)₂, Cu, 18.0%; N, 3.97%. It has been found that cobalt(II), nickel and nitrate do not interfere in the estimation of copper(II) in the pH-range of 3.7 to 4.7.

The analysis of this chelate displayed the metal-ligand ratio to be 1 : 1 and the absence of water. The molecular weight of the chelate in benzene was found by Ebuliometry to be 695 ± 15.

An infrared analysis of the copper(II) chelate indicated the absence of the characteristic absorption frequency for -OH group in it. Guoy apparatus gave 1.89 B.M. as the magnetic moment of the copper(II) chelate at 300°K. The electronic absorption spectra of this chelate in dioxan and pyridine consist of two absorption bands at 23,810 and 14,080 cm⁻¹, the former band being stronger than the latter.

Results and Discussion

The results of gravimetric estimation of Cu(II) by the procedure given earlier are summarized in Table 1.

The copper(II) chelate exists as an unsolvated dimer, which is evident from its molecular weight. Infrared spectroscopy shows the absence of the characteristic frequencies of the -OH group in it. Elemental analysis of the chelate indicated 1 : 1

TABLE 1. RESULTS OF GRAVIMETRIC ESTIMATION OF COPPER(II)

Weight of chelate (mg)	Copper (mg)		Error (%)
	Found	Taken	
271.91	48.88	48.98	0.20
243.22	40.25	40.37	0.19
214.33	35.50	35.58	0.22
199.65	33.06	33.14	0.24
154.74	25.64	25.69	0.19

metal-ligand ratio and also suggest the absence of water molecules. The magnetic moment was found to be 1.89 B.M. at 300 K. The electronic absorption spectra in dioxan and pyridine consists of two bands with peaks at 23,810 and 14,080 cm^{-1} , the first being the stronger. The band at 14,080 cm^{-1} , is a d-d band. The other band at 23,810 cm^{-1} is an intra-ligand charge transfer band. Elemental analysis, molecular weight, magnetic moment and the spectral data may be best explained by assigning a non-planar dimeric structure (I) for the copper(II) chelate. In this structure the four coordination positions of the cupric ion are fully satisfied and these ions are situated at the opposite ends of an eight-membered ring so that direct Cu-Cu bonding does not take place. Consequently superexchange is prevented and the chelate would display normal magnetic moment. Thus structure (I) explains satisfactorily

all the experimental data given earlier. This structure is also in agreement with that of the copper(II)

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complex of N-salicylidene anthranilic acid investigated by Kubo³.

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